

Sustainable Transformation of Individuals and Families: Design and Implementation of Holistic Personalised Socially-driven Persuasive Systems

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ABSTRACT

The sustainability concept emphasises improvement of our quality of life with the balancing of economic benefits, human rights and ecological concerns. As individuals and families are at the core, a basic component of society, applying the sustainability concept to the individual and family level can ultimately result in sustainable societal transformation. However, there are few systems that have models and processes to support an individual's sustainable transformation, based on a holistic understanding of the dynamics of multiple life dimensions. Most systems fail to motivate or persuade sustained behavioural transformation. Overall, there is a paucity of research on the design and implementation of systems to support the sustainable transformation of Individuals, and the problem is exacerbated when we consider systems that could help the transformation of families. Information systems have the potential to play a critical role in supporting sustainable transformation, especially with the current prevalence of smart and wearable devices and systems. To address the above-mentioned lacuna, this research uses a multi-methodological design science approach. This research proposes and implements concepts, models, frameworks, and architectures that are central to the sustainable transformation of individuals and families. The research synthesises ideas and concepts from holistic, personalised, socially-driven, and/or persuasive systems. In particular, the proof of concept implementations of this research will 1) help collect and integrate various individuals and families' data on multiple dimensions, 2) analyse via a spectrum of models the dynamics and relationship among the data, 3) provide personalised information on habit formation and sustainable transformation, and 4) provide persuasive recommendations for sustainable transformation. As part of this research, a system that facilitates individuals' and families' sustainability decisions has been prototyped in the context of shopping. The ideas and concepts implemented here have been generalised and a generic prototypical system to support sustainable habit formation through games is underway.

Keywords: individual and family sustainability, sustainable social shopping, habit formation, sustainable transformation systems

RESEARCH BACKGROUND

Sustainability has surfaced to the centre of our attention in recent years. Although different stakeholders developed the concept broadly by incorporating their interests, the generally accepted idea of sustainability encompasses economic development, social equity, and environmental protection (Murphy & Drexhage, 2012). As such, the sustainability concept aims to give holistic guiding principles to businesses and organisations who traditionally advocate sustainable development at the global level (Sneddon, Howarth, & Norgaard, 2006). Recently the concept has diffused downward to capture the attention of individual and family's roles in sustainability (Nawroth, 2013). While businesses and organisations' main foci of sustainability are ecological and environmental responsibilities, individual and family's foci of sustainability are more concerned about health, well-being and leading a balanced lifestyle. Despite the growing interests of individual and family sustainability, it has not yet been formally

identified, defined and developed and does not possess the holistic guiding principles that businesses and organisations do.

Most of us aspire to well-being and balanced lifestyles. Therefore, people are constantly improving their living status by pursuing their life goals. It is a transformation process conducted through a series of decision-making and action taking. People consciously and subconsciously try to make the best decision based on their situation. This decision-making process is significantly affected by data and information acquired in various aspects of life – health, career, education, family relationship, social status, and so on. As human life is composed of many dimensions (Habermas, 1984), this engenders requirements for holistic presentation of information and insightful recommendations, which shows dynamics and interrelation relationships among the life dimensions. Unfortunately, studies on the multifaceted activities and dimensions are rare and under-developed.

Similar to individual's decision-making and transformation processes, the family also makes decisions and go through transformation processes based on phases in family life. Carter and McGoldrick (1989) identify six stages of family life cycle and explain major events at each stage. From the family system theory perspective, families make unique decisions through the interaction of family members. At the same time, these decisions also significantly influence each and every family member (Balswick & Balswick, 2007). For example, a family may decide to move to a rural place as the parents generation retires. This family decision can in turn impact on other family member's health, career and social relationships. Therefore, the family level decision-making is even more complex, as it involves not only a more intense utilisation of information, but also multiple dimensions and the interaction of members within a family.

To make an effective decision, we often turn to information systems and in particular decision support systems. Decision support systems collect, process and analyse data to contextualise a decision environment for users (Turban & Aronson, 1997). For the personal decision-making, personalised preferences and multifaceted data should be collected and analysed (Chung, 2006). With the development of smart technologies and wearable devices, individuals and families have become heavy users of information and communications technology (Baskerville, 2011). Individuals' and families' activities leave traces of data daily, to be collected and analysed by information systems. In particular, the movement called "quantified-self" shows a recent trend of using technologies to collect various personal data, such as physical exercises, biometric data, sleep patterns, food habits and financial data. Although these systems and technologies are designed for behavioural changes and habit formation of individual users, several challenges should be addressed before they could effectively support the sustainable transformation of individuals and families.

Firstly, there is a huge difference in the pace of systems development between individuals and families. Due to the recent trend of self-tracking, numerous activity tracking applications and systems have been developed for individuals, but not for families. While some information systems have been developed for families with special needs (<https://www.childwelfare.gov/>) or family health management (Bonacina, Marceglia, Bertoldi, & Pinciroli, 2010), these systems are designed for organisations, who manage family issues, and not for the families themselves. This asymmetric development between individuals and families systems may hinder the progress of the sustainable lifestyle transformation, as the relationship between individuals and families is intimate and their lives are tightly intertwined.

Secondly, individual self-tracking tools rarely offer cross-dimensional services. The activity tracking systems provide data and information logging features for their health, finance or environmental contribution data, etc. The biggest quantified-self movement community "Quantifiedself.com" provides guides for around 505 self-tracking tools, classified with different tags. The majority of tags are health related keywords, as are a few tags for careers, finance, environment and social keywords. In most cases, one tool covers only one life dimension. For example, although fitbit and digifit (the first two tools introduced in the guide) have multiple tags, they are all related to the health dimension.

Thirdly, integration of heterogeneous data is hardly offered in self-tracking systems and technologies. To gain competitive advantage and larger market share, recently these tools are offering more features to capture various data. For example, fitbit captures steps, exercise, weight, food intake, and sleep pattern data and shows all data in one place. Although these different health data give a picture of user's health to some degree, they do not tell how each type of health data contributes to a user's overall health. The root

problem is because the system does not have the models to understand and analyse causal and interrelated relationship among the data. Therefore, it is hard to offer personalised and persuasive recommendations under these circumstances.

To facilitate the users' action taking, various motivational features are offered in self-tracking systems and technologies. It is important to make these systems and technologies efficacious as the real values and benefits will come when the user can form intended habits. It was believed that a habit can be formed within 21 days (Maltz, 2002). However, it has proven to be a myth (Selk, 2013). Lally, Van Jaarsveld, Potts, and Wardle (2010) find that, on average, it takes up to 66 days to form a habit. The variations across participants range between 18 and 254 days. The sustainable transformation is a long-term process, where time and willpower will be needed to make observable changes. As willpower is limited and runs out through the day (Kelly McGonigal, 2011), techniques that promote the persistence of individuals become all the more valuable, and should be implemented into the systems (Fritz, Huang, Murphy, & Zimmermann, 2014). Some self-tracking systems and technologies use gamification, goal setting and social community features as motivational techniques. However, most of these motivational tools are not personalised to offer a strong motivation (Conroy, Yang, & Maher, 2014) nor designed for the sustainable transformation of individuals and families. Notwithstanding the rapid development in self-tracking systems and technologies, supporting the entire sustainable transformation of individuals and families to develop holistic, personalised socially-driven persuasive systems is still rather challenging to accomplish.

PRACTICAL PROBLEMS AND RESEARCH ISSUES

The literature and system review helped us to identify key problems and issues:

1. There is a paucity of research on formalising the concept of individual and family sustainability.
 - Insufficient efforts have been spent in understanding the importance of a holistic view of our lifestyle, causal and interdependent relationships among various life dimensions.
 - The concept has not been formally established and there are no holistic guiding principles for individuals and families.
2. Lack of research interest in studying the multi-dimensional richness of human activities and lifestyle from the individual and family sustainability point of view.
 - Causal relationship models of life dimensions are under-developed and under-studied.
 - Decision support and recommendation models are under-developed for individual and family sustainability.
3. Few systems support the transformation process for individual and family sustainability.
 - Studies at the individual level outnumber and dominate those at the family level.
 - Few systems measure the multi-dimensional daily data of individuals and fewer systems have models and frameworks that integrate heterogeneous daily data and interpret their relationships in a holistic manner for individuals and their families.
 - While many systems support a single habit formation process, few systems support multiple inter-connected transformation processes holistically.
 - Few systems provide personalised decision support and recommendations by integrating online social networks for individual and family sustainability.
4. Many systems fail to motivate/persuade sustained behaviour changes.
 - Applications and services that offer well-established persuasion techniques for bridging user's intention to behavioural changes are rare.
 - While many applications and systems use gamification and online social networks as motivational features, not many of them are designed for the full sustainable transformation.

Overall, the research on personalised persuasive decision support and recommendation systems for individual and family sustainability systems is insufficient. The biggest challenges are heterogeneous data integration from different life dimensions – i.e. health, wealth, relationships or careers, etc. and providing holistic, integrated information for personalised persuasive recommendations to users. All identified research problems are connected to the principal issue of pursuing individual and family sustainability.

RESEARCH AIMS, OBJECTIVES, AND METHODOLOGY

The preceding explanations illustrated several key problems and issues connected to establishing individual and family sustainability and implementing the concept in the information and decision support systems context. These can be categorised as being conceptual, procedural and technological in nature. Quantified-self movements have emerged and started to form a one of the fastest growing industries with significant resources being pumped into technological development, yet limited concepts, models, and conceptual frameworks have been developed and practised to provide insightful holistic information for individual and family sustainability.

The aim of this research is to define “Individual and Family Sustainability and their sustainable transformation” by synthesizing the sustainability concepts, persuasive technology, personalised information systems, habit formation, transformation and online social networks. Based on these we then propose and design conceptual and system artefacts to develop systems which support individual and family sustainability by applying socially-driven multi-dimensional approach. Particularly this research will focus on the design and implementation of Sustainable Social Shopping Systems (SSSS) and Personalized Persuasive Systems for Individual Sustainability (PPSIS).

The research aims discussed in the previous section lead us to the following research objectives:

1. Define and establish holistic “Individual and Family Sustainability” concept. This will provide clear definition and boundary of individual and family sustainability for future studies.
2. Identify influential factors for “Individual and family Sustainability” from the multi-dimensional and holistic view of our lifestyle.
3. Identify problems, issues and requirements for the design and implementation of systems to Sustainable Transformation for Individuals and Families (STIF).
4. Design of conceptual artefacts (models, processes, and frameworks) that support the sustainable transformation of individuals and families. The goal is to facilitate a move towards individual and family sustainability and continuous improvement by proposing the required steps and relationships.
5. Validate the conceptual and system artefacts by implementing two proof of concept systems (a) Sustainable Social Shopping Systems and (b) Persuasive Systems for Individual Sustainability
6. Evaluate the proof of concept prototypes through observational, analytical, experimental, testing and descriptive methods (Hevner, March, Park, & Ram, 2004).

This research makes use of a multi-methodological research approach comprising of the design science methodology suggested by Nunamaker, Chen, and Purdin (1990) and Hevner, March, Park, and Ram (2004) due to the holistic nature and range of the outlined research objectives. Insightful academic literature and existing system review (i.e. observation) is the starting point to develop an understanding of theoretical background for the individual and family sustainability. This observation step will then lead us to proposing various conceptual theoretical artefacts to underpin the system design and building. In the system development stage, system artefacts for Sustainable Social Shopping System (SSSS) and Personalised Persuasive Systems for Individual Sustainability (PPSIS) will be designed and implemented as the part of systems to Sustainable Transformation for Individuals and Families (STIF). In the evaluation step, the research will adopt the design evaluation guide from Hevner et al. (2004) to validate functionality, usability, and effectiveness of systems. The multi-methodological approach that we adopt provides an iterative and incremental research process.

RESEARCH CONTRIBUTIONS

This research brings benefits to researchers in several disciplines. Primarily IS researchers can better understand how to design and implement individual and family oriented information systems. These have implications, especially for the design of decision support systems (DSS), recommender systems (RS), holistic systems (HS) that provide personalised persuasive information and recommendations for individuals and families. System and data integration models and frameworks will guide them to address the problems from heterogeneous, distributed and autonomous individual information systems. Secondary behavioural science, education, and marketing researchers can better understand human behaviours and real motivations for human developments through critical data and models. This research also benefits users of systems. The research will design and implement two systems (i.e. SSSS and PPSIS)

for the individual and family sustainability and their sustainable transformations. By using the integrated systems, users can observe and analyse their daily activities and form series of positive habits to reach a sustainable lifestyle. As the core concept of this research is individual and family sustainability, various life dimensions are considered and reviewed for designing and implementing systems for STIF. The developers of holistic, personalised, social-driven, and persuasive systems can be anticipated to benefit from this research, as they can utilise the conceptual and system artefacts for these systems developed by this research.

REFERENCES

- Balswick, J. O., & Balswick, J. K. (2007). *The Family: A Christian Perspective on the Contemporary Home*. Baker Publishing Group.
- Baskerville, R. (2011). Design Theorizing Individual Information Systems. *PACIS Proceedings 2011*, (Pacis), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1057/ejis.2011.8>
- Bonacina, S., Marceglia, S., Bertoldi, M., & Pincioli, F. (2010). Modelling, designing, and implementing a family-based health record prototype. *Computers in Biology and Medicine*, 40(6), 580–590. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combiomed.2010.04.002>
- Carter, B., & McGoldrick, M. (1989). *The Changing Family Life Cycle: A Frameworks for Family Therapy*. New York: Gardner Press.
- Chung, R. (2006). *Integrated Personal Recommender Systems*. The University of Auckland.
- Conroy, D. E., Yang, C. H., & Maher, J. P. (2014). Behavior change techniques in top-ranked mobile apps for physical activity. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 46(6), 649–652. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amepre.2014.01.010>
- Fritz, T., Huang, E. M., Murphy, G. C., & Zimmermann, T. (2014). Persuasive technology in the real world: a study of long-term use of activity sensing devices for fitness. *Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 487–496. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2556288.2557383>
- Habermas, J. (1984). The theory of communicative action. *Book*, 1(1), v. <https://doi.org/10.1086/228287>
- Hevner, A. R., March, S. T., Park, J., & Ram, S. (2004). Design Science in Information Systems Research. *MIS Quarterly*, 28(1), 75–105. <https://doi.org/10.2307/25148625>
- Kelly McGonigal. (2011). *The Willpower Instinct: How Self-Control Works, Why It Matters, and What You Can Do To Get More of It*. New York: Penguin Group.
- Lally, P., Van Jaarsveld, C. H. M., Potts, H. W. W., & Wardle, J. (2010). How are habits formed: Modelling habit formation in the real world. *European Journal of Social Psychology*, 40(6), 998–1009. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ejsp.674>
- Maltz, M. (2002). *New Psycho Cybernetics*. Penguin Group.
- McTigue, K. M., Conroy, M. B., Hess, R., Bryce, C. L., Fiorillo, A. B., Fischer, G. S., ... Simkin-Silverman, L. R. (2009). Using the internet to translate an evidence-based lifestyle intervention into practice. *Telemedicine Journal and E-Health : The Official Journal of the American Telemedicine Association*. <https://doi.org/10.1089/tmj.2009.0036>
- Murphy, J., & Drexhage, D. (2012). *Sustainable Development : From Brundtland to Rio 2012. United Nations*. Retrieved from http://www.un.org/wcm/content/site/climatechange/pages/gsp/documents_1
- Nawroth, C. (2013). CSR and Sustainability in Times of Crisis: Are Consumers Voting with Their Wallets and Are Companies Putting Their Money Where Their Mouth Is? *Uwf UmweltWirtschaftsForum*, 21(1–2), 75–81. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00550-013-0273-4>
- Nunamaker, J., Chen, M., & Purdin, T. (1990). Systems Development in Information Systems Research. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 3(7), 89–106. <https://doi.org/10.1109/HICSS.1990.205401>

Selk, J. (2013, April 15). Habit Formation: The 21-Day Myth. *Forbes*. Retrieved from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/jasonselk/2013/04/15/habit-formation-the-21-day-myth/#30619742debc>

Sneddon, C., Howarth, R. B., & Norgaard, R. B. (2006). Sustainable development in a post-Brundtland world. *Ecological Economics*, *57*(2), 253–268. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2005.04.013>

Turban, E., & Aronson, J. (1997). *Decision Support Systems and Intelligent Systems*. *Decision Support Systems and Intelligent Systems*. Retrieved from <http://www.amazon.co.uk/dp/0131230131>